

Electrical Conductivity of Salts of Alkaloids in Pure and in Mixed Solvents.

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To study the influence of introduction of alcohol in aqueous solutions of substances on their electrical conductivity, solutes chosen by previous investigators had solubilities in water considerably different from those in alcohol. Solubilities of salts of alkaloids in water and in alcohol being not so much different, it was thought worth while to ascertain how their conductivities would be influenced by the presence of alcohol in their aqueous solutions. The mixtures of solvents used in the present investigation were in molecular proportions, which enabled direct comparison of the molecular-conductivity figures of one solute with those of another. Some of the relevant investigations on the subject may be briefly mentioned in this connection. The conductivity of aqueous solutions of electrolytes is lowered by the addition of alcohol to varying extents (Schall, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1894, **14**, 701). The lowering of molecular conductivity of sodium chloride and potassium chloride by the presence of alcohol in their aqueous solution, for 1 per cent. of alcohol, is not so great for the later additions of alcohol as it is for the first additions (Hantzsch, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1900, **25**, 332). The conductivity of a salt may be caused to decrease with the rise of temperature by the addition of 1 to 20 per cent. of any aliphatic alcohol (Bartoli, *Gazzetta*, 1894, **ii**, **24**, 156; *Abstracts*, 1895, **68**, **ii**, 6).

Conductivities of aqueous-alcoholic solutions of some salts were determined when approximately limiting values were obtained for infinite dilutions in some cases only. Several instances have been found where limiting value for infinite dilution was not obtained (Vollmer, *Ann. Phys. Chem.*, 1894, **ii**, **52**, 3), and instances have also been found where maximum results were obtained (Jones and co-workers, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, **32**, 521; 1906, **36**, 325). It has been noted by Tymstra (*Abstracts*, 1903, **84**, **ii**, 623) that maximum molecular conductivity is dependent not only on the dilution of the solution but also on the composition of the solvent. Influence of the composition of the solvent, when mixtures of water and alcohol are used, on the molecular conductivities of acids has also been

worked out by Goldschmidt, Schjerve and Feigl (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1914, **89**, 129). Arrhenius has investigated many electrolytic aqueous solutions with regard to the influence on their conductivity by the addition of various non-electrolytes in varying quantities (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1892, **9**, 487). The decrease of conductivity brought about by the addition of 1 per cent. by volume of the non-electrolyte depends on the nature of both of the electrolyte and of the non-electrolyte.

Cohen's researches are quite interesting in this connection. He noted that dissociation of a substance in aqueous solution could be measured either by the determination of electrical conductivity or by the measurement of the velocity of inversion of cane sugar. But the replacement of some water by alcohol has no effect on the degree of dissociation of the dissolved material as could be determined from the electrical conductivity (Cohen, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1898, **25**, 1; 1899, **28**, 145), whereas the velocity of inversion of cane sugar by hydrochloric acid in aqueous solution is diminished by the addition of alcohol.

All the above investigators have tried to generalise using their results in all sorts of ways which are often more or less divergent amongst themselves. This difficulty in arriving at a general conclusion has also been felt in studying the results obtained by the determination of molecular conductivity of hydrochlorides of alkaloids in solution in water, in alcohol and in mixtures of water and alcohol. Conclusion, however, can be drawn under the circumstances that a molecule present in a solution is interdependent to all others present in the field, but it remains to be established to what extent such interdependency is related to or comparable to chemical reaction.

The measurement of molecular conductivity was carried out by the usual method with an induction coil and telephone keeping the cell in a water-bath fitted with an electric stirrer. The temperature of 35° was considered to be suitable for the purpose of such determinations at this tropical place, and this was kept constant throughout the experiment within $\pm 0.1^\circ$. Ordinary conductivity water was used in these experiments and the alcohol was purified by refluxing with freshly burnt quick-lime for 3 days, and after distillation had a specific conductivity 6.148×10^{-6} mhos which agreed well with what was obtained by White (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **133**, 1413).

Very pure alkaloids were used in the preparation of salts used in these experiments. These pure free bases gave the following molecular conductivities in aqueous solutions prepared by occasionally.

shaking finely powdered substances with conductivity water for 7 days. Quantities of morphine, codeine and narcotine present in their respective aqueous solutions were determined by evaporation of known volume of each one and the strength of cotarnine in its aqueous solution was ascertained by titration with *N*/10-sulphuric acid.

Molecular conductivities of free bases.

	ν	35°
Morphine, $C_{17}H_{19}O_3N$	556.6	55.4
Codeine, $C_{18}H_{21}O_3N$	36.8	3.8
Narcotine, $C_{12}H_{15}O_7N$	2065.0	198.0
Cotarnine, $C_{12}H_{15}O_4N$	4.16	11.1

Hydrochlorides of morphine, codeine and cotarnine were prepared by neutralising dilute solutions of the acid with dry finely powdered base and recrystallising three times from conductivity water, and finally dried in steam-oven. Narcotine hydrochloride could be conveniently prepared by passing dry hydrochloric acid gas through benzene or alcoholic solution of pure narcotine. Narcotine hydrochloride separates forthwith from benzene solution of the base on passing the acid gas as a white crystalline deposit; and from the alcoholic solution it separates as fine crystalline mass on evaporation of alcohol on steam-bath. The salt thus prepared, is dried in a steam-oven, powdered and kept in a vacuum desiccator over quicklime over 4 days.

Solvents used in the following determinations of molecular conductivity at 35° were pure water, pure alcohol, or mixtures of water and alcohol in exactly calculated molecular proportions as given below, and dilution of the solutions during a series of measurements was effected by pipettes.

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Narcotine hydrochloride, C₂₂H₂₃O₇N, HCl.

Dilution in litres per gram molecule (<i>v</i>).	% EtOH mols. ...		50		80		90		95		99		100
	0	5	10	30	50	20	10	5	1	5	1	0	
8	193.21	156.21	114.21	71.21	44.23	26.38	20.41	19.92	17.21	14.36			
16	216.31	172.30	125.40	81.41	51.34	35.45	34.31	23.41	22.46	16.81			
32	225.40	173.71	136.30	87.31	60.68	42.53	29.88	29.24	27.37	20.73			
64	246.20	191.33	137.20	92.46	63.71	48.61	35.34	33.21	34.48	25.72			
128	254.21	200.74	139.41	94.36	67.31	56.72	42.40	41.23	44.35	28.21			
256	256.24	200.81	140.24	94.21	67.40	59.81	54.62	44.34	49.46	35.34			
512	258.37	204.01	140.60	94.01	70.81	61.41	52.62	44.28	50.21				
1024	258.21	203.31	140.40	94.19	—	—	—	—	—	—			

Cotarnine hydrochloride, C₁₂H₁₅O₄N, HCl.

8	106.41	77.31	58.41	38.12	31.12	25.16	24.11	24.24	23.34	23.14			
16	114.17	84.61	63.12	42.41	35.41	30.29	26.12	26.21	26.10	25.16			
32	118.48	90.34	66.70	45.62	39.34	34.34	33.11	31.13	31.62	29.21			
64	123.41	96.46	69.61	47.21	41.21	38.21	35.41	35.41	36.42	34.32			
128	127.61	98.31	73.34	50.34	43.81	39.81	38.32	37.61	38.21	37.45			
256	132.10	104.36	74.61	52.17	43.22	44.61	42.41	42.21	42.12	42.36			
512	134.07	105.71	74.43	52.12	44.81	44.21	44.36	44.08	44.01	44.42			
1024	148.40	113.11	82.32	—	—	—	—	—	—	—			

Resistances becoming very great, determinations at higher dilutions of solutions containing large quantities of alcohol were not very accurate. It is seen from these results that these salts of alkaloids are conductors of electricity in solutions in water, in alcohol and in mixtures of water and alcohol. Molecular conductivity decreases as the water in the solution is replaced by alcohol keeping the volume unchanged. Such decreasing influence of alcohol is somewhat similar when solutes are similar in molecular structure but not so when they are different.

If molecular conductivity of codeine hydrochloride in *N/16*-solution in solvents of varying composition from pure water to pure alcohol be divided by that obtained under identical condition of hydrochloride of any other alkaloid, it would be found that the quotients thus obtained are neither constant nor vary uniformly with the variation of the solute. Such variation of results could also be obtained if molecular conductivities of codeine hydrochloride in solutions other than *N/16* are similarly divided.